

FLEXURAL BEHAVIOUR OF HOLLOWCORE SLABS STRENGTHENED WITH PRESTRESSED CARBON FIBER REINFORCED POLYMER PLATES

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ABSTRACT

Strengthening structures with externally prestressed carbon fiber reinforcement polymer (CFRP) plates has been proven to be an effective method to improve the serviceability and the ultimate performance of the concrete structures. However, it has not been widely used in the field due to the challenges associated with the prestressing and anchoring techniques. This paper presents a part of a comprehensive experimental program aiming to investigate the flexural behaviour of full-scale prestressed hollow-core slabs (PHCS) strengthened with externally bonded and unbonded prestressed CFRP plates using a novel field-applicable wedge anchorage system. The tested slabs were strengthened with bonded and unbonded CFRP plates using various prestressing levels. The ultimate and cracking loads were increased by as much as 31.5% and 25%, respectively, for the strengthened slabs compared to the control slab. In addition, a significant enhancement of 95% in the ductility was observed for the slab strengthened with bonded and anchored plates.

KEYWORDS

Strengthening; Hollowcore slabs; Prestressed concrete; Externally bonded; Externally unbonded; Rehabilitation; Anchorage system; Precast concrete

INTRODUCTION

Prestressed hollow-core slabs (PHCS) are precast concrete slabs that have been widely used in residential, industrial, and infrastructure projects. PHCS have many advantages over conventional reinforced concrete slabs including low self-weight, higher ultimate load capacity with lower reinforcement ratio, long spans, structural efficiency, enhanced serviceability, and speed of construction. Similar to other reinforced concrete structures, PHCS may need strengthening or rehabilitation to enhance their existing structural capacity to address unexpected increase of service loads, and strength reduction. Possible causes for strength reduction include damage of the prestressing strands, material deterioration such as corrosion, mechanical and electrical penetrations. Therefore, efficient structural rehabilitation methods are required to recover strength and serviceability performance of the degraded concrete members (Yang et al., 2009). Strengthening and rehabilitation of PHCS could be a cost-effective alternative to replace a deteriorated structure, or, in fact, the only available solution for a situation where service shut down of a structure is unfeasible.

Carbon fiber-reinforced polymer (CFRP) systems have been used in the flexural strengthening of concrete structures worldwide. The increasing popularity of CFRP composites is attributed to their high strength-to-weight ratio, excellent fatigue resistance, and corrosion resistance when compared to other strengthening materials (ACI 440.2R-17, 2017; Kim & Heffernan, 2008; Meier, 1995). Although different forms of CFRP have been used in strengthening applications, more effective strengthening can be achieved using CFRP plates. This is due to their relatively large cross-sectional areas which eliminates the need of multiple-layer application, good conforming surface area of contact with structures which does not require epoxy-filled channels as in the case of near-surface-mounted, resulting in low installation cost.

Repair of structures can be categorized into passive and active methods. Passive repair refers to the engagement of the strengthening materials by sharing and redistributing of the stresses caused by the application of additional loads (Hong & Park, 2017). The application of non-prestressed CFRP materials is an example of passive repair. Although flexural strengthening with non-prestressed CFRP material (passive repair) increases the ultimate capacity of the concrete member, it has little effect on its serviceability performance (i.e., cracking, yielding, and deflection). In addition, flexural strengthening with non-prestressed CFRP does not fully utilize the high tensile strength of the CFRP material (Hong & Park, 2017). Unlike the passive repair, an active strengthening system induces external forces to counteract existing stresses (i.e., dead and live load) or to restore prestress losses in prestressed concrete structures (PCS). Research studies have shown that strengthening with prestressed CFRP can result in an efficient use of the material and a better utilization of its high tensile strength (El-Hacha et al., 2001; Nordin, n.d.; Nordin & Täljsten, 2006). This improvement is more noticeable with high prestressing levels (Rezazadeh et al., 2014). The concept of strengthening with externally prestressed bonded and unbonded CFRP composites has been investigated by several researchers as reported by Havez & Al-Mayah, (2023). In bonded applications, the CFRP composites are prestressed and attached to the concrete substrate using epoxy adhesive with and without anchorage systems. In unbonded applications, the CFRP composites are anchored at their ends to the concrete member. The main challenge with strengthening reinforced concrete structures with prestressed CFRP laminates is associated with their premature debonding failure. Premature debonding of CFRP occurs with high prestressing levels and/or in the absence of an efficient anchorage system (El-Hacha et al., 2003; Quantrill & Hollaway, 1998). This is due to the high shear stresses over the area where the prestress forces are transferred from the CFRP plates to the concrete (Aram et al., 2008; Kotynia et al., 2013; Nader Tehrani et al., 2019; Xue et al., 2010). Although debonding and slippage of CFRP laminates can be prevented or delayed by using a reliable anchorage system (Kotynia et al., 2013; Pellegrino & Modena, 2009; Quantrill & Hollaway, 1998), it is crucial to consider the field applicability of the prestressing system (i.e. anchorage and its attachment to concrete) on large scale concrete elements (Hong & Park, 2016). Given that the end of most slabs, beams, and girders in existing buildings is not accessible, the prestressing system should be capable to directly tension the CFRP plates by jacking and reacting against the concrete element itself rather than an external frame. It is worth mentioning that most of the recent research work focused on the application of prestressed CFRP composites to conventional RC structures and relatively little work conducted on strengthening internally prestressed concrete structures (Aram et al., 2008; Czaderski & Motavalli, 2007).

This paper presents a part of a large experimental program aiming to investigate the flexural behaviour of strengthening full-scale PHCS with externally bonded and unbonded CFRP plates subjected to various prestressing levels. Three slabs were tested under four point-bending up to failure including one control unstrengthened slab. The remaining two slabs were strengthened with bonded and unbonded CFRP plates prestressed to 19% and 72% of the plate ultimate strength level, respectively, using a site applicable mechanical anchor and prestressing system.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

Specimen details

The research program comprised of three large-scale PHCS tested under static loading up to failure as shown in Table 1. The slabs were cast at a local precast concrete plant and had a standard cross-section dimension of 1219 mm x 203 mm, and 6000 mm long as shown in Figure 1. The slabs were reinforced with four straight 7-wire strands (9.53 mm diameter) prestressed up to 70% of their ultimate tensile strength. The bottom concrete cover to the steel strands was kept constant at 35 mm. A standard profile with low reinforcement ratio (4 strands instead of regular 5 strand) was selected to mimic a slab with degraded performance caused by prestress losses or strands damage where a tension failure by rupture of the steel tendons or the CFRP plate prior to concrete crushing was expected. The CFRP plate had a cross section of 50 mm x 1.2 mm with a design tensile strength of 2800 MPa.

Table 1: Test matrix

	Span length (mm)	Thickness (mm)	Reinforcement	Mechanical Anchor	CFRP Plate	Prestressing level
HC (Control)	5700	203	Four 9.5mm 7-wire strands	--	--	--
HC-B20-M				Anchored	Bonded	20%
HC-U70-M				Anchored	Unbonded	70%

*A percentage of the design tensile strength of the CFRP plate (target value)

The specimen's notation is as follows: the first two letters 'HC' refer to the hollowcore slab. The following letter represents whether the CFRP was bonded 'B' or unbonded 'U'. The following number represents the prestressing level applied to the CFRP plate as a percentage of its ultimate tensile strength. The letter 'M' indicates whether the mechanical anchor was present or not. One slab acted as a control unstrengthened slab HC1. The second slab HC-B20-M was strengthened in positive bending with one bonded prestressed CFRP plate, and was prestressed up to 19% of its ultimate tensile strength and bonded to the underside surface of the slab using high strength epoxy paste adhesive (Sikadur-30). The prestress force was transferred immediately after the required prestressing level was achieved and prior to resin cure. Hence, eliminating the contribution of the the adhesive bond to the prestress transfer mechanism. The third slab HC-U70-M was strengthened with unbonded CFRP plate prestressed up to 72% of its ultimate tensile strength.

A field applicable prestressing system was developed and utilized in the experimental testing as described in a subsequent section. Each slab had four top openings at each end through its middle cores. These openings were filled solid with grout (Sikagrout 112) for the screw anchors used to fasten the prestressing system.

a) Cross section

b) Top view of the slab

Figure 1: Slab configuration

Casting

The slabs were cast in a local precast plant on a steel casting bed. The steel bed was 1219 mm wide and 92000 mm long. The bed was cleaned and oiled before the strands were pulled individually and tensioned up to 70% of their ultimate strength. The concrete was transported from the batching and mixing area through an over-head tank discharging into the extruder. The extruder was programed to the chosen slab profile and ran on wheels on side rails of the casting bed to compact and form the concrete, as shown in Figure 2. Thirty-five concrete cylinders (100 mm in diameter x 200 mm long) were cast from different batches, in compliance with the CSA standards, and placed on top of the casting bed during the curing process. The slabs were covered with tarps over night for curing. After the minimum transfer concrete strength (28 MPa) was achieved, the tension in the strands were released and the slabs were cut at the required length. The slabs were then transferred to the structural lab at the University of Waterloo for testing.

a) Cast bed

b) Precast hollowcore slabs

Figure 2: Casting hollowcore slabs

Material properties

Normal weight concrete mix with 19 mm nominal maximum aggregate size and zero slump was used. The mix had specified 28-compressive design strength of 50 MPa and minimum specified transfer strength of 28 MPa. Compressive strength tests were conducted on the concrete cylinder at the day of prestress transfer, 3 days, 7 days, and 28 days. The average compressive strength at 28 days for concrete was 74 MPa. Internal seven-wire low relaxation strands (9.53 mm diameter) with ultimate tensile strength of 1860 MPa and modulus of elasticity of 198.6 GPa were used for this study. The CFRP plate known commercially as Carbodur S512 (SIKA, Canada) and high strength epoxy paste adhesive (Sikadur-30) were utilized in strengthening the slabs. Table 2 shows the design values, provided by the manufacturer, for the mechanical properties of the CFRP plate and the epoxy adhesive.

Table 2: Mechanical properties of the CFRP and epoxy adhesive

	CFRP plate	Epoxy adhesive
Type	Carbodur S512	Sikadur-30
Dimensions (mm)	50 x 1.2	--
Tensile strength (MPa)	2800	24.8
Compressive strength (MPa)	--	59.3
Modulus of elasticity (GPa)	165	4.5
Elongation at break	> 1.7%	--

Prestressing assembly and anchorage system

The CFRP plate was tensioned using three wedge anchors, prestressing assembly, and two hydraulic jacks. The wedge-type anchors were developed at the University of Waterloo and comprised of a barrel and two wedges (Alhusain & Al-Mayah, 2022). The CFRP plate was placed between the two wedges. In addition, two heat-treated copper plates inserted between CFRP and the wedges to improve the gripping before pre-setting the wedges into the barrel using a hammer. A prestressing assembly was developed as a part of this study in collaboration with the industrial partner to ensure its field applicability. The system can directly tension the CFRP plates by jacking and reacting against stay-in place anchors fastened to the underside of the slab rather than an external frame. Therefore, eliminating the need of end access to the strengthened slab. The prestressing assembly comprised of a live-end unit where the prestress is applied using two hydraulic jacks, and a fixed dead-end unit. Both live and dead ends were fastened to the underside of the slab using commercial concrete screw anchors to eliminate over-head vertical epoxy application. The hydraulic jacks were connected to the live end unit using steel plates and bolts as shown in Figure 3. The live and dead end units incorporated two adjustable pillow blocks and a roller. The roller system was used to change the CFRP angle with minimal friction and reduce the gap between the CFRP and the concrete surface. One anchor was seated at the dead end and one through the back plate at the live end, with the third anchor (between the two at the live end) left unseated between the hydraulic cylinders. After the prestressing of the CFRP plate was completed, a small bearing plate along with two threaded rods were used to seat the third anchor by pushing the wedge into the barrel to minimize prestressing losses. The hydraulic jacks and the steel plates are then removed before testing. The initial applied prestress force was recorded using two load-cells between the hydraulic jacks and the back plate. Prestress losses were monitored using strain gauges mounted on the CFRP plate.

a) Prssestressing assembly - live end top view

b) Prestressing assembly - dead end side view

d) Fabricated prestressing system
Figure 3: Prestressing system

Instrumentation and test set-up

The large-scale slabs were tested under four-point bending on simple supports as shown in Figure 4. The center-to-center dimension between the supports was 5700 mm with a shear span of 2350 mm. For the strengthened slabs, the two stay-in place prestressing systems were mounted at each end to underside of the slab as shown in Figure 5. The distance between the two units was 4100 mm. The load was applied by servo-hydraulic actuator of 2600 KN capacity and controlled by Shore-western SC6000 controller. The load was applied under displacement control at a rate of 1 mm per minute. The midspan deflection was measured using one linear variable differential transducer (LVDT) and two String Potentiometer placed at the top and the bottom of the slab. Two Electrical resistance strain gauges (Tokyo Sokki Kenkyujo Co., Ltd.) having a gauge length of 1 mm were bonded to the steel strands to measure the strains at midspan. Three strain gauges for composite material having a gauge length of 5 mm were mounted on the CFRP plate to measure the strain at mid span and near the prestressing ends. The concrete compression strain was measured using two 90 mm concrete strain gauge mounted on top of the concrete surface at midspan. Steel strand slippage was measured using an LVDT mounted horizontally using a clamp system fixed at the end of the slab as shown in Figure 6. The data was recorded using National Instrumentation Data Acquisition System.

Figure 4: Test setup schematic (all dimensions are in mm)

Figure 5: Prestressing assembly mounted to the underside of the slab

Figure 6: Strand slippage measurements using LVDT

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Table 3: Preliminary study test results

	HC1 (control slab)	HC-B20-M	HC-U70-M
Ultimate load (KN)	54.7	69.66	72.04
Cracking load (KN)	49.7	53.68	62.1
Deflection at cracking (mm)	6.45	5.8	8.253
Deflection at failure (mm)	132.6	213	150.7
Max. CFRP Strain ($\mu\epsilon$)	N/A	8,327.44	12,265.59
Prestressing Level in CFRP *	N/A	19%	72%
Mode of failure:	Steel rupture followed by concrete crushing	Steel rupture followed by concrete crushing	---

*A percentage of the design tensile strength of the CFRP plate

Figure 7: Prestressing of CFRP plate for HC-U70-M

Figure 8: Flexure failure of HC1

a) HC-U70-M after failure

b) Dead-end anchor after failure

c) CFRP fracture after failure

d) Live-end anchor after failure

Figure 9: Flexural failure of HC-U70-M

Figure 10: Flexural cracks during testing (HC-B20-M)

Stiffness is one of the main parameters used for serviceability limit design of prestressed concrete elements. The deflection response of the slabs at midspan is plotted against the applied load as shown in Figure 11. The effect of the prestress level was significant on the ultimate deflection, and insignificant on the deflection corresponding to the cracking load. The deflection at failure for HC-B20-M and HC-U70-M was 60% and 14% higher than the control slab, respectively. The deflection at ultimate for HC-B20-M was 196% higher than the control slab, and almost identical to the control slab for HC-U70-M. Stiffness at cracking was defined as the ratio of cracking load to the corresponding displacement. The stiffness at cracking for HC-B20-M was 20% higher than the control slab, and almost identical to the control slab for HC-U70-M. In addition, a notable impact was observed on the post cracking flexural stiffness for the slabs strengthened with prestressed CFRP plates when compared to the control specimen.

The ultimate energy absorption capacity, defined as the area underneath the load-deflection curve up to failure load, for HC-B20-M and HC-U70-M was 95% and 28% higher than the control specimen, respectively. Therefore, enhancing the ability of the slab to withstand a sufficient deformation beyond the elastic limit while maintaining an adequate load carrying capacity until total failure.

The strains measurements due to flexural loading in the CFRP plate with respect to the applied loads for HC-B20-M and HC-U70-M are shown in Figures 12 and 13, respectively. After initial cracking of the concrete, a sharp increase in the CFRP tensile strains was observed for the strengthened slabs. At ultimate, higher maximum CFRP strain readings were recorded for HC-U70-M compared to HC-B20-M. A maximum total strain of approximately 49% of the CFRP rupture strain was obtained for HC-B20-M compared to 72% for HC-U70-M. The concrete strain in compression continuously increased with increasing load and changed nonlinearly after initial cracking as shown in Figure 14. In addition, the strengthened slabs exhibited lower concrete compression strains at the same load level when compared to the reference slab. Similarly, the steel strains increased linearly prior to initial cracking with lower values corresponding to the bonded specimen HC-B20-M due to the effect of the composite action. The post cracking behaviour was not reported due to damage of strain gauges.

Figure 11: Load versus mid-span deflection for HC1, HC-B20-M, and HC-U70-M

Figure 12: Load versus CFRP strain for HC-B20-M

Figure 13: Load versus CFRP strain HC-U70-M

CONCLUSIONS

Three large-scale prestressed hollowcore slabs were cast and tested under four point-bending up to failure. One slab was a control unstrengthened slab, and the other two slabs were strengthened with bonded and unbonded CFRP plates using various prestressing levels. A site applicable prestressing system utilizing wedge anchors was developed to tension the CFRP plate by jacking and reacting against a stay-in place anchors fixed to the underside of the slabs. Preliminary results endorsed the efficiency of the strengthening technique by showing enhancement in both ultimate and serviceability performance of the strengthened slabs. Higher ultimate and cracking loads and better ductility behaviour were observed for the strengthened slabs compared to the reference slab. The ultimate and cracking loads were increased by as much as 31.5% and 25%, respectively, for the strengthened slabs compared to the control slab. In addition, a significant enhancement of 95% in the ultimate energy absorption capacity was observed for the slab strengthened with bonded and anchored plate. The slab strengthened at 70% prestress level exhibited higher strengthening efficiency, lower concrete tensile strains, and higher CFRP strain utilization at failure than the one strengthened at 20% prestressing level which allowed for an efficient use of the CFRP material's high tensile strength.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial and in-kind support provided by Fritz-Alder Precast and Mitacs.

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